

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**UTERINE ADENOMYOSIS AND INFERTILITY IN
WOMENS: A STUDY CARRIED OUT A MAYO HOSPITAL
LAHORE**¹Dr. Nasrullah Zeeshan, ²Dr. Aroosa Khalid, ³Dr. Muhammad Salman Akhtar¹Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore²Punjab Medical College Faisalabad³WAPDA Hospital Complex, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objectives: The aim of this study is to conclude the demographic design and clinical performance of 23 barren ladies along with intraoperative analysis of adenomyosis and after that histopathologic authentication.

Methodology: An evaluation of 23 sequential barren women who experienced surgical procedure because of before operation wrong judgment for uterine fibroids in a 5 years' timeframe.

Results: The age range of the patients was 26 to 47 years (mean 37.3). Out of 23 patients, 21.7% (5) patients had a past history of delivery and 78.3% (18) patients were underwent through abortion(s) in the past. Primary sterility found in 21.7% and secondary in 78.3%. Past history of (i) antenatal processes comprising of dilatation and curettage in 73.9% (17) patients, (ii) myomectomy in 21.7% (5) patients and (iii) adhesiolysis in 13.1% (3) patients. Pre-surgery hysterosalpingogram with consensual tubal patency indicated 8.7% (2) patients and 73.9% (17) patients had mutual tubal blockage. Perceived the fallopian tube's individual patency in 17.4% (4) patients. Cornual blockages were bump into 88.2% (15) patients amongst the 17 bilateral tubal blockage patients. The clinical presentation modes were having 100% abdominopelvic mass, 82.6% dymenorrhoea, 60.9% menorrhagia, 47.8% dyspareunia and in 34.8% cases were metrorrhagia. Intraoperatively adenomyosis confronted were include 56.5% (13) patients with diffuse adenomyosis, 30.4% (7) patients with multiple focal adenomyosis and 13.1% (3) patients with unifocal adenomyosis. Out of 23 patients, co-existing uterine fibroid were coming across in 73.9% (17) patients and coexisting endometriosis in 8.7% (2) patients. Momentous pelvic linkage was encounter in to 30.4% (7) patients at surgery.

Conclusion: Adenomyosis is expressively link along proximal tubal occlusion in barren women and wants to subsist with irrelevant uterine fibroids.

Key Words: Anticipated Pathophysiologic, Endometriosis, Adenomyosis, Proximal Tubal, Dymenorrhoea, Immunologic.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Nasrullah Zeeshan,
Allama Iqbal Medical College,
Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Nasrullah Zeeshan et al., **Uterine Adenomyosis and Infertility in Womens: A Study Carried Out a Mayo Hospital Lahore.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Adenomyosis is a kind of gynecological situation described through expansion in stroma and endometrial gland in uterine musculature. Although the adenomyosis' etiopathogenesis is not completely comprehend, however, at endometrial myometrial interface (EMI), hypothesis commencing from deficiency of basement membrane to damaged membrane have assumed [1]. Hormonal imbalance is the other anticipated pathophysiologic process in neonates which is causing into faulty distinction of myometrial and stromal cells with ensuing tendency to adenomyosis in maturity [2]. Recently, biochemical [4, 7] and immunologic [3] elements have been associate to adenomyosis. On the hypothesis based, distraction or automated EMI connection damage can result into adenomyosis, peril aspects are disturbance to uterus from abortion and childbirth. Additional hazardous influences are hyperoestrogenemia, chronic hereditary factors endometritis [1, 8].

Barrenness and adenomyosis are barely relate to one another as adenomyosis is a state that is generally discover after the forty years' age. There may be increase in the diagnostics of adenomyosis because of general delay in the pregnancy and avoidance of childbirth in our women because of career achievement. Adenomyosis correct identifying is generally poor and full of errors which caused into late verdict and

treatment initiation. Adenomyosis management is tough and clumsy. Leiomyoma is a frequent differential finding of adenomyosis. Similar to the presented case series, in few occurrences, misjudgment has mistakenly steered to surgical involvement [9]. Keeping in view the aforesaid, we assessed the 23 successive barren women's clinical presentation, demographic variables and in-operational discoveries, which, during assessment and infertility workup were mistakenly diagnose as leiomyomata and the intraoperative findings were adenomyosis.

METHODOLOGY:

A forthcoming assessment of those 23 successive barren women who were undergo through surgery because of wrong diagnosis of uterine fibroid before operation and during operation finding was adenomyosis uteri. This research was completed in the duration of 5 years from 2012 to 2017 in Mayo Hospital Lahore. All the 23 patients were undergoing through evaluation for barrenness. Before operation they had hysterosalpingography and abdominal sonography. Biopsy was performing during operation along with or without de-bulking. Tissues were expose to histopathologic check (Figures-1&2). All the patients were sufficiently encouraged and advocated after operation.

Figure 1

Figure 2

RESULTS:

The age of the patients was range from 26 to 47 years with a mean age of 37.3 years. Out of 23, 82.6% (19) patients ages were 35 years and above. Primary infertility accounted for 5 (21.7%) patients whereas, secondary infertility was in 18 (78.3%) patients. out of the 23 patients' 21.7% (5) patients were having past myomectomy history. Past history of infertility for more

than 10 years was in 19 patients (82.6%). Seventeen (73.9%) patients out of 23, comprised of earlier curettage and dilatation history, 13.0% (3) patients had past adhesiolysis record for uterine synechia. Previous record of obstetric revealed that out of 23 patients, 78.3% (18) patients had previous abortions history and 21.7% (5) patients had positive child birth record (Table-1).

Variables		No of Patients (n=23)	%age
Age	< 30 years	2.0	8.70
	30 to 40 years	14.0	60.90
	41 to 50 years	7.0	30.40
Type of infertility	Primary	5.0	21.70
	Secondary	18.0	78.30
Duration of infertility	1 to 10 years	4.0	17.40
	11 to 20 years	12.0	52.20
	21 to 30 years	7.0	30.40
Previous childbirth	0	18.0	78.30
	1	3.0	13.10
	2	1.0	4.30
	3	1.0	4.30
Previous abortions	None	5.0	21.70
	Spontaneous	5.0	21.70
	Induced	13.0	56.50
Previous uterine / Intrauterine procedure	Dilatation and curettage/ MVA	17.0	73.90
	Adhesiolysis	3.0	13.10
	Myomectomy	3.0	13.10

MVA - Manual Vacuum Aspiration

Clinical appearances were mostly consisting of 100% abdominopelvic mass, 82.6% dysmenorrhea, 60.9% menorrhagia, 47.8% dyspareunia and in 34.8% metrorrhagia. Before operation hysterosalpingogram discovered that 8.7% (2) patients having bilateral tubal patency, 17.4% (4) patients having unilateral tubal blockage and 73.9% (17) patients having bilateral tubal blockage. Fifteen out of 17 patients with bilateral tubal blockage and all 4 patients of unilateral tubal blockage were having cornual tubal blockage site (Table-II).

Table-II: Clinical Presentation		
Variable	No of Patients (n=23)	Percentage
- Symptoms and signs		
Abdominopelvic mass	23.0	100.00
Dysmenorrhoea	19.0	82.60
Menorrhagia	14.0	60.90
Dyspareunia	11.0	47.80
- Tubal finding on HSG		
Bilateral tubal patency	2.0	8.70
Bilateral tubal blockage *Cornual (15) *Distal (2) Unilateral tubal blockage	17.0	73.90
*Cornual (4)	4.0	17.40

After operation, all HSG re-assessed prior surgery revealed that HSG of one patient having the specification of adenomyotic results of minute various spicules spreading towards myometrium from the endometrium (Figure-3).

Figure-3: Hysterosalpingographic findings

Ten (43.5%) patients were found with main adenomyosis between operation and thirteen (56.5%) patients were having scattered adenomyosis. In seventeen (73.9%) patients coexisting uterine fibroid was discovered, out of which 76.5% (13) patients were having irrelevant fibroid saplings. Co-existing endometriosis was found in only 8.7% (2) patients. Seven (30.4%) patients found with pelvic adhesion, out of which four were having past myomectomy (Table-III). Out of 23 patients all of them exhibited biopsy from the involved myometrium, six had biased local expurgation and only one patient may possibly be placed on gonadotrophin releasing hormone analogue.

Table-III: Intraoperative Findings		
Variable	No of Patients (n=23)	Percentage
Uterine size		
12 - 20 weeks size	14.0	60.90
> 20 weeks size	9.0	39.10
Type of adenomyosis		
Diffuse	13.0	56.50
Focal	10.0	43.50
Coexisting fibroid *Insignificant seedling (13) *Significant fibroid (4)	17.0	73.90
Coexisting endometriosis	2.0	8.70
Presence of pelvic adhesion	7.0	30.40

* type of fibroid () Number

DISCUSSION:

The adenomyosis uteri detection remains a hard finding that is nervous through faults. It is due to clinical appearance is alike to more general type of gynecological states as like endometriosis and leiomyoma. Moreover, the adenomyosis' imaging diagnostic traits are irregular and adjustable on MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) and sonography [10]. An extraordinary catalog of mistrust is therefore requiring for adenomyosis detection. Although, the usual

diagnostics of adenomyosis was on hysterectomy sample's pathologic investigation, the MRI and TVS (transvaginal sonography) induction into clinical performance transformed and improved the diagnostic ratio of adenomyosis. Although MRI and TVS both are good in detection of adenomyosis, however, MRI is a little more preferred and better due to distinction and better recognition of the imaging features [11]. In assessments before operation, none of our patients had MRI or TVS. All of them had TAS (transabdominal

sonography) which is associated to poor sensitivity and resolution [12, 13]. However, it was assuring that all cases in our study were wrongly detected as leiomyoma. Adenomyosis is an ailment of multiparous and premenopausal ladies [8, 9]. On the other side in our series, only 8.6% patients were multiparous, while all of them were premenopausal. In our study majority of the patients (78.2%) had the past history of abortion. This might validate the mechanical loss (trauma hypothesis) to endometrial myometrial interface (EMI) in adenomyosis' aetiopathogenesis [14, 15]. The significant number of our patients that had past history of intrauterine procedure further authenticate this hypothesis. The motive of association of adenomyosis to infertility is not completely clear. Yet, the clarification is position around EMI as an efficient part that is made-up of sub-endometrial myometrium and basal endometrium. This functional unit is significant in placental development, conservation of pre-implantation blastocyst, sperm transportation, and embryo implantation [16]. In the non-menstrual period of a woman, these acts are attaining over backward shrinkage of sub-endometrial myometrium [17, 18]. In our series of patients, noteworthy is the more tubal occlusion percentage at cornua. Biopsy was accomplishing on myometrium with adenomyotic tissue for all patients intraoperatively and post histopathologic analysis, this validate our findings. Biopsy (Blind random needle) has been co-relate to less sympathy in the adenomyosis analysis; since the consequence of the effect is reliant on the complexity/degree of mucosal intrusion through biopsies and adenomyotic tissue [19]. The only offered treatment form was incomplete erasure of the concerned myometrium in 6 out of 23 patients. The other conventional managing forms are laparoscopic vessel embolization, myometrial electrocoagulation and endomyometrial ablation [20]. Because of the patient's desirousness for fertility in our study, hysterectomy was not a choice and the same statement can be applying for infertile women with endomyometrial ablation as a treatment form.

The handling of hormones by using GnRH (gonadotrophin releasing hormone) analogue; in one patient zoladex was engage after operation which caused in indicative development and decreasing in size of uterine, though perception was not reach. Live births and pregnancies has recorded in other studies after management through GnRH analogue [21, 22]. The hormonal treatment more types incorporate anti-oestrogen, progestogen, oral contraceptive and intrauterine devices laden with danazol or levonorgestrel. Combination of GnRH analogue treatment and surgery (micro-surgical whole resection) have been use with achievement in live births and perception [23, 24]. In the adenomyosis uteri

management, the usage of HIFU (high-intensity focused ultrasound) is a hopeful traditional treatment form [10].

CONCLUSION:

We come across a solid relationship amongst intrauterine procedures and past abortion history with adenomyosis. Moreover, the discovered higher cornual tubal occlusion ratio demands more research for this issue.

REFERENCES:

1. Chopra S, Lev-Toaff AS, Ors F, Bergin D. Adenomyosis: common and uncommon manifestation on sonography and magnetic resonance imaging. *J Ultrasound Med* 2006; 25:617-27.
2. Tamai K, Togashi K, Ito T, Morisawa N, Fujiwara T, Koyama T. MR imaging findings of adenomyosis: correlation with histopathologic features and diagnostic pitfalls. *Radiographics* 2005; 25:21-30.
3. Udewela AS, Perera MAD, Aiqing L, Fraser IS. Endometrial - myometrial interface: relationship to adenomyosis and changes in pregnancy. *Obstet Gynecol Survey* 2000; 55:390-400.
4. Lyons EA, Taylor PJ, Zheng XH, Ballard G, Levi CS, Kredentser JV. Characterization of subendometrial myometrial contractions throughout the menstrual cycle in normal fertile women. *Fertil Steril* 1991; 55:771-4.
5. Kuligowska E, Deeds L III, Lu K III. Pelvic pain: overlooked and underdiagnosed gynaecological conditions. *Radiographics* 2005; 25:3-20.
6. Parrott E, Butterworth M, Green A, White INH, Greaves P. Adenomyosis - a result of disordered stromal differentiation. *Am J Pathol* 2001; 159:623-30.
7. Ota H, Igarashi S, Hatazawa J, Tanaka T. Is adenomyosis an immune disease? *Hum Reprod Update* 1998; 4:360-7.
8. Ota H, Igarashi S, Hatazawa J, Tanaka T. Immunohistochemical assesment of superoxide dismutase expression in endometriosis and adenomyosis. *Fertil Steril* 1999; 72:129-34.
9. Ota H, Igarashi S, Kato N, Tanaka T. Aberrant expression of glutathione peroxidase in eutopic and ectopic endometrium in endometriosis and adenomyosis. *Fertil Steril* 2000; 74:313-8.
10. Ota H, Igarashi S, Sasaki M, Tanaka T. Distribution of cyclo-oxygenase-2 in eutopic and ectopic endometrium in endometriosis and adenomyosis. *Hum Reprod* 2001a; 16:561-6.
11. Ota H, Igarashi S, Tanaka T. Xanthine oxidase in eutopic and ectopic endometrium in endometriosis and adenomyosis. *Fertil Steril* 2001b; 75:785-90.
12. Byun JY, Kim SE, Choi BG, Ko GY, Jung SE, Choi

- KH. Diffuse and focal adenomyosis: MR imaging findings. *Radiographics* 1999; 19:161-70.
13. Devlieger R, D'Hooghe T, Timmerman D. Uterine adenomyosis in the infertility clinic. *Hum Reprod* 2003;9(2):139-47.
 14. Siedler D, Laing FC, Jeffrey RB, JR Wing VW. Uterine adenomyosis. A difficult sonographic diagnosis. *J Ultrasound Med* 1987; 6:345-9
 15. Bohlman ME, Ensor RE, Sanders RC. Sonographic findings in adenomyosis of the uterus. *Am J Roentgenol* 1987; 148:765-6.
 16. Azziz R. Adenomyosis: current perspectives *Obstet Gynecol Clin North Am* 1989; 16:221-35.
 17. Mori T, Ohta Y, Nagasawa H. Ultrastructural changes in uterine myometrium of mice with experimentally induced adenomyosis. *Experientia* 1984; 40:1385-7.
 18. DeVries K, Lyons EA, Ballard G, Levi CS, Lindsay DJ. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1990; 162:679-82.
 19. Popp LW, Schwiedessen JP, Gaetje R. Myometrial biopsy in the diagnosis of adenomyosis uteri. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1993; 169:546-9.
 20. Wood C. Surgical and medical treatment of adenomyosis. *Hum Reprod Update* 1998; 4:323-36.
 21. Huang FJ, Kung FT, Chang SY, Hsu TY. Effects of short-course buserelin therapy on adenomyosis. *J Reprod Med* 1999; 44:741-4.
 22. Silva PD, Perkins HE, Schauburger CW. Life birth after treatment of severe adenomyosis with a gonadotropin - releasing hormone agonist. *Fertil Steril* 1994; 61:171-2.
 23. Lin J, Sun C, Zheng H. Gonadotropin - releasing hormone agonists and laparoscopy in the treatment of adenomyosis with infertility. *Chin Med J* 2000; 113:442-5.
 24. Wang PH, Yang TS, Lee Wl, Chao HT, Chang SP, Yuan CC. Treatment of infertile women with adenomyosis with a conservative microsurgical technique and a gonadotropin - releasing hormone agonist. *Fertil Steril* 2000; 73:1061-2.